

LATIN LANGUAGE AS AN INTERNATIONAL LANGUAGE OF SCIENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11402544>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 21-may 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 25-may 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 31-may 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

communication, international language, Experimental Physics, analytical means, autocinetum

ABSTRACT

This article talks about the role and importance of the Latin language on an international scale. It provides information on the role, importance, and use of the Latin language in world science from the period of its emergence and development until now, based on analyzes. In addition, the use of terms and their aspects in every field of the Latin language today is discussed.

Introduction

Latin language as the international language of science and fiction significantly distinguishes it from the numerous artificial languages proposed for international communication - both from those that received at least limited distribution, and from the incomparably larger part of them, which remained stillborn projects. Being the official language of the multi-tribal Roman Empire, which occupied by the 3rd century. AD a vast territory around the Mediterranean Sea, Latin turned out to be the only cultural language in its western part. It retained this significance even after the fall of the Western Roman Empire in the 5th century. under the pressure of barbarian tribes. Up to the XII - XIII centuries. Latin remained the only literary language, an instrument of artistic creativity and scientific thought, but above all, the language of the Catholic religion, which formed the basis of medieval ideology.

In the oral speech of numerous Romanized tribes, the Latin language changed so much that already in the 3rd - 4th centuries. it developed into a number of local dialects, collectively called Vulgar Latin. Subsequently, these dialects laid the foundation for modern Romance languages. The written Latin language, despite all the diversity of areas in which it was used, did not lose its unity: mastery of it opened up for its speakers the possibility of mutual live communication both in Romanized countries and beyond their borders.

Analysis and results

The compilers of an excellent anthology of medieval Latin literature write: "The Latin language was not a dead language, and Latin literature was not dead literature. They not only wrote in Latin, but also spoke: it was a spoken language that united the few educated people of that time: when a boy - a Swabian and a Saxon boy met in a monastery school, and a Spanish youth and a Pole youth met at the University of Paris, then in order to understand each other, they had to speak Latin. And not only treatises and lives were written in Latin, but also accusatory ones. sermons, and meaningful historical works, and inspired poems. The Latin poem "Valtarius" developed the plots of ancient Germanic tales long before the "Song of

the Nibelungs", and the Provençal troubadours and German minnesingers learned lyrical themes and techniques from their older contemporaries - the Latin vagant poets. And those same Latin theological treatises that so frighten today's readers were a school of dialectics for European thought, modern and useful"[5].

Thus, for many centuries before the Renaissance, the Latin language flawlessly performed the functions of an international language, and not only in science, but also in poetry.

The Renaissance, having established a strict classical norm for the Latin language, significantly limited the possibilities for the free development of New Latin literature and thereby created an additional incentive for the development of literature in the emerging national languages. The gradual and steady retreat of the Latin language in this area must be recognized as a positive moment of cultural development. The situation is different in the scientific field. Science by its very nature is international, and for it the presence, along with national languages, of a single language that serves the purposes of international communication is a beneficial factor. It is therefore quite understandable that here the position of the Latin language turned out to be more stable and it retained its importance even when the national languages of Europe, borrowing Latin and Latinized Greek vocabulary, became effective tools of scientific creativity.

The era of harmonious symbiosis of the Latin language as an international language and national languages as its equivalent successors was the 18th century.

An example of this is the scientific activity of M.V. Lomonosov using, as a rule, the Latin language in his works on chemistry, physics, astronomy, mineralogy, Lomonosov translated many of these works into Russian and with these translations, as well as the translation of Wolf's "Experimental Physics," he created the basis of Russian natural science terminology. For obvious reasons, he gives preference to the Russian language in works on Russian history, but scientific polemics in this area, addressed to the academic community, are conducted in Latin (comments on Miller's dissertation). He also resorted to Latin in scientific correspondence addressed to foreign scientists - Euler, Formei, in a letter of gratitude to the Swedish Academy of Sciences. For Lomonosov, the Latin language was in the full sense of the word a living language - the engine of creative thought, thereby containing an inexhaustible source of development of new and new expressive possibilities. The study of the Latin language not only by many of Lomonosov's contemporaries, but also by scientists of a later time should have led to the same conclusion.

At the same time, already in the 18th century, but at an even faster pace in the 19th and 20th centuries. Under the influence of the steady growth of national movements, the Latin language is being replaced by national ones, and this causes obvious damage to the intensity of scientific communication, and thereby to scientific work as a whole.

In addition to the indicated main reason, another factor, seemingly of a directly opposite nature, had a negative impact on maintaining the traditions of living Latin - the emergence of the idea of a universal language, created artificially and intended to become the common and only language of mankind. The first significant attempts in this direction date back to the 17th century, i.e. to the time when the Latin language fully satisfied all the needs of international communication in the scientific field. But the requirements that the century of rationalism made for the "philosophical" language - in its vocabulary and grammatical structure to unambiguously reflect the entire diversity of things and relationships - the Latin language satisfied as little as any of the national languages.

Despite the fact that practice has shown the complete unreality of such a broad formulation of the problem, many projects of this type followed one after another. A kind of stable tradition of understanding the international language as artificial was created, which remained valid even when the international language began to be assigned a more limited, but also more real role as an auxiliary language, intended only for certain areas of human communication.

In 1909, the Italian mathematician G. Peano proposed a project for an international language called "interlingua", the essence of which is revealed in its other name - "Latin-sine-flexione" (Latin without inflections).

This is a language completely oriented towards Latin and latinized vocabulary, and in relation to the grammatical system, built on the principle that Peano formulated as follows: the smallest theoretically possible amount of grammar is the absence of any grammar. Of course, this formulation is nothing more than an effective play on words; in reality, we are talking about the rejection not of grammar, which would constitute a linguistic absurdity, but only of the inflectional expression of grammatical forms. Thus, if the Latin inflection phrase *patre ama filio* has a certain meaning, it is because the grammatical meanings (which in the equivalent Latin phrase *filium amat pater* are conveyed by inflection) are here expressed by word order. In other cases, grammatical meanings can be expressed by analytical means. But one way or another, with the destruction of inflection, a new system of expression must be created to replace it, and the expressive capabilities of the language will be preserved only to the extent that this immutable condition is met.

Indeed, the new system seems simpler and easier to digest than inflected Latin grammar, which, despite its generally recognized clear consistency, contains many "anomalies." However, when deciding on the choice of a language officially accepted as the international language of science, it is necessary to take into account the following considerations, which determine the special place of the Latin language in the culture of our time.

1. Although the Latin language has lost the importance of the international language of scientists of any specialty, which belonged to it back in the 18th century, in a number of scientific fields its position remains unshakable at the present time. First of all, it is the language of natural science taxonomy dating back to Linnaeus, as well as anatomical, medical and pharmacological nomenclature. At the same time, Latin and Latinized Greek vocabulary serves as the main source of replenishment of the continuously and progressively growing terminology in all areas of science and technology.

2. Latin is the main language of European culture from antiquity to modern times, and without it it is impossible to independently comprehend the most important facts of this culture from primary sources, and, consequently, no truly historical education.

3. The Latin language, if properly organized in its teaching in the system of secondary and higher schools, would be one of the means of increasing the level of philological education, which in itself is very important. Even when the study of Latin is aimed primarily at mastering practical skills in oral and written speech, it must be based on a philological analysis of classical texts, and this is what will give it the most important educational value, regardless of the particular practical benefits achieved.

L.V. Shcherba pointed out that as a result of the abolition of the study of ancient languages after the revolution and a significant reduction in educational time allocated to new foreign languages, "our Soviet school turned out to be almost completely devoid of elements of linguistic education, contrary to the centuries-old tradition that remains strong almost all over the world and now.

A prominent French mechanical scientist, director of the National Institute of Applied Knowledge, Professor Jean Capel published an article under the expressive title "Latin or Babylonian pandemonium" (*"L'Education Nationale"* 10/23/1952), in which he developed the idea that in the conditions of the rapidly growing multilingualism of scientific literature, the need for an international language is becoming increasingly urgent, and since no national language in this function would meet with the necessary unanimous support in all countries, the only solution to the problem is to bring the present functioning of Latin as the international language of science to such a level that in which it would satisfy the needs of communication in all areas of science.

A significant place in the work of the congress was occupied by questions of methods of teaching the Latin language. A common feature of the reports and debates devoted to these issues was the desire to simplify the teaching of grammar and focus on students' acquisition of practical skills in Latin speech.

Conclusion

Ways were outlined to enrich Latin vocabulary in accordance with the requirements of modern science:

- 1) the use of the existing huge lexical material of late and medieval Latin, including epigraphy, to denote new concepts;
- 2) critical use of material from humanistic and neo-Latin fiction and scientific literature, in particular dictionaries related to special disciplines;
- 3) creation of neologisms based on Latinized Greek vocabulary;
- 4) Latinization of modern Greek scientific and technical terminology (hamaxostichus "train", autocinetum "car");
- 5) periphrastic transmission of new language terms;
- 6) finally, for cases when all these sources turn out to be insufficient, the preservation of the new language term (gas, radar). A very important result of the work of the congress was the adoption of a uniform, universally binding, so-called restored pronunciation of Latin words (pronuntiatio restituta).

Congress addressed the editors of scientific journals with a proposal to accompany the articles they published with Latin summaries. Broader objectives were outlined at the initiative of the Institute of Roman Studies by the International Congress for the Promotion of Latin Education and the Latin Language (Rome, April 1966). Without eliminating the question of the practical use of Latin as an international language, which was central to the previous "French" congresses of living Latin, the Institute of Roman Studies put it in connection with the general problem of the place of the Latin language in modern culture.

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